

Green Banking Initiatives Taken By Indian Banking Sector

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Abstract Banking Sector is never considered as a polluting industry. This sector plays an important role between economic growth and environmental protection. This kind of banking is known as Green Banking. It includes Green Finance: Green Mortgage, Green Loan, Green checking of Accounts, Green banking Activities: Mobile Banking and Online Banking, and Waste Management: Power Saving Equipment, use of solar and Wind Energy. In this paper an attempt has been made to create awareness amongst general public regarding Green Banking initiatives taken by the Bank.

Keywords Green Finance, Green Mortgage, Green Loan, Green Banking.

Introduction Green Banking means promoting environmentally friendly practices and reducing your carbon footprint from your banking activities. This comes in many forms:

1. Using online banking instead of branch banking.
2. Paying bills online instead of mailing them.
3. Opening up CDs and money market accounts at online banks, instead of large multi-branch banks.
4. Finding the local bank in your area that is taking the biggest step to support local green initiatives.

The Banking Sector influences the economic growth and development in terms of both quality and quantity, there by changing the nature of economic growth. Banking sector is one of the major sources of financing investment for commercial projects which is one of the most important economic activities for economic growth. Therefore, banking sector can play a crucial role in promoting environmentally sustainable and socially responsible investment (SRI). Banks may not be the polluters themselves but they will probably have a banking relationship with some companies/ investment projects that are polluters or could be in the future.

Banking Sector is generally considered as environmentally friendly in terms of emissions and pollutions. Internal environmental impact of the banking sector such as use of energy, paper and water are relatively low and clean. Environmental impact of banks is not physically related to their banking activities but with the customer's activities. Therefore, environmental impact of bank's external activity is huge though difficult to estimate. Moreover, environment management in the banking business is like risk management. It increases the enterprise value and lowers loss ratio as higher quality loan portfolio results in higher earnings. Thus, encouraging environmentally responsible investments and prudent lending should be one of the responsibilities of the banking sector. Further, those industries which have already become green and those, which are making serious attempts to grow green, should be accorded priority to lending by the banks. This method of finance can be called as "Green Banking", an effort by the banks to make industries grow green and in the process restore the natural environment. This concept of "Green banking" will be mutually beneficial to the banks, industries and the economy.

Green Banking coverage includes:

Green Finance: Green Mortgage, Green Loan, Green Checking of Accounts.

Green Banking Activities: Mobile Banking and Online Banking.

Waste Management: Power Saving Equipment, use of solar and wind energy.

Objective of study

1. To study the concept and identify the steps necessary to adopt green banking.
2. To create awareness about green banking initiative among the general public

Review of Literature

Nanda Sibabrata and Bihari Suresh (2012) Green Banking has been an integral part of the banking system in the world's developed and developing economies. Much research has been carried out on the concept of green banking and the possible benefits of its implementation. This study tests the relationship between the implementation of green banking along with two other variables, net income and expenses, and the profitability in India using a fast data panel regression. The result of the study shows significant relationships between net income and expenses with profitability, whereas no significant relationship between the implementation of green banking and profitability was proven.

Yadav Rambalak and Pathak Govind (2014) from the study it was analysed that public sector banks are emphasizing more on green initiatives as compared to the Private Sector Banks except ICICI Bank. The private sector banks except ICICI bank are mainly inclined towards green initiatives such as net banking, mobile banking which are needed by the bank to match with the competitors as all the banks are providing these facilities. The environmentally friendly activities such as energy efficient alliances, implement green data centres help in improving their operational efficiency as well as cost saving in the long run. Whereas public sector banks along with the ICICI bank are taking various initiatives such as creating environmental awareness among society, giving more preference to environmentally friendly commercial projects, promoting the pollution control measures, promoting Environment Management System certification etc. along with the basic green initiatives such as paperless banking, energy efficient products recycling etc.

Dr. Jha Nishikant and Bhome Shraddha (2013) did the empirical study on the steps that can be taken for going green in the banking sector and to check the awareness among bank employees, associates and the general Public about green banking concept. They did this study by collecting data from 12 bank managers, 50 bank employees and 50 general customers. The authors were of the opinion that online banking, green banking, power saving equipments, green credit card, use of solar and wind energy and mobile banking were some of the strategies that should be followed for going green.

Result and Discussion

Need of Green Banking

Until recently, environmental concerns were not considered relevant to the business operation of banks and financial institutions. Traditionally, banking sector's concern for environmentally degrading activities of clients is like interfering or meddling in their business affairs. However, now it is being perceived that dealing with environment brings risks to their business. Although the banking and financial institutions are not directly affected by the environmental degradation, there are indirect costs to banks. Due to strict environmental disciplines imposed by the competent authorities across the countries, the industries would have to follow certain standards to run their business. In the case of failure, it would lead to closure of the industries leading to a likelihood of default to the bank. For example, the enactment of CERCLA in the US in late 1980s has resulted in huge loss to the banks in the US as banks held directly responsible for the environmental pollution of their clients and made to pay the remediation cost. This is the reason for which banks in the US are ahead of other countries in integrating environmental concerns into their business operations. In the recent years several other countries (more in Europe) are seen adopting policies that have made banks responsible for the misdeeds of their clients. Therefore, the financial institutions need to engage proactively with the stake holders on environmental and social policy issues and evaluate the impacts of their client's investment. In turn, that would force the customers to take care of their management of environmental and social policy issues relating to investment. This should cover all project financing activities across all industries. The importance of green banking is immense for both the banks and economy by avoiding the following risks involved in banking sector.

Credit risk

It can arise indirectly where banks are lending to customers whose businesses are adversely affected by the cost of cleaning up pollution or due to changes in environmental regulations. The cost of meeting new requirements on emission levels may be sufficient to put some companies out of business. Credit risks may be higher

due to the probability of customer default as a result of uncalculated expenses for capital investment in production facilities, loss of market share and third-party liability claim. Credit risks are also associated with lending on the security of real estate whose value has diminished owing to environmental problems (additional loss in the event of default). Further, the risk of loan default by debtors due to environmental liabilities due to fines and legal liabilities and reduced priority of repayment under bankruptcy.

Legal risk

It can occur in different forms. Obviously, banks like other companies are at risk if they do not comply with relevant environmental legislation. But more specifically, they are at risk of direct lender liability for cleanup costs or damages claims if they have taken possession of contaminated or pollution-causing assets. An environmental management system helps a bank to reduce risks and costs, enhance its image, and take advantage of revenue opportunities.

Reputation risk

In all likelihood, due to growing awareness about environmental safety, banking institutions are more prone to lose their reputations if they are involved in big projects, which are viewed as socially and environmentally damaging.

The adoption of green banking strategies will help the bank to deal with these risks involved in their business operation. Green banking strategies involves two components:

1. Managing environmental risk, and
2. Identifying opportunities for innovative environmentally oriented financial products (IFC, 2007)

To manage environmental risk, the banks have to design proper environmental management systems to evaluate the risks involved in the investment projects. The risks can be internalized by introducing differential interest rates and other techniques. Moreover, banks can withdraw itself from financing high-risk projects. The second component of green banking entails creating financial products and services that support commercial development with environmental benefits. These includes investment in renewable energy projects, biodiversity conservation, energy efficiency, investment in cleaner production process and technologies, bonds and mutual funds meant for environmental investments etc.

Initiative taken by Indian Banks

Public Sector Banks

State Bank of India (SBI) (Statistics as per Annual Report 2014-15)

1. SBI had launched Green Channel Counter (GCC) facility at their branches in 2010 to change the traditional way of paper-based banking (SBI, 2014)
2. The Bank had also collaborated with Suzlon Energy Ltd for the generation of wind power for selected branches by setting up of Windmills in Gujarat, Tamil Nadu & Maharashtra (Business Standard, 2014).
3. It has become a signatory to the Carbon Disclosure Project in which they undertake various environmentally and socially sustainable initiatives through its branches spread across the length and breadth of the country.
4. Export-Import Bank of India (EXIM) and SBI entered into an agreement to jointly provide long-term loans up to 14 years to Spain-based company Astonfeild Renewable Resources and Group T- Solar Global SA for building solar plant in India. Most of the financial institutions avoid giving long-term loans to such projects because of their uncertainty and technological changes.
5. Bank has adopted energy efficient measures.
6. SBI is the largest deployer of solar ATM's.
7. Bank has installed windmills in three states for its own energy needs.
8. Paperless Banking is promoted and implemented across the country.
9. Gives project loans at concessionary rate of interest to encourage reduction of greenhouse gases by adopting efficient manufacturing processes.

Punjab National Bank (PNB)- (Statistics as per annual report 2014-15 and per their websites)

1. The Bank has been actively pursuing the social policies since two-thirds of branches of the bank are in rural and semi-urban areas where the CSR is the core of normal day-to-day banking operations.
2. Punjab National Bank has been proactively catering to the needs and aspirations of the society and small & micro entrepreneurs and youth in particular. Towards improving the livelihood of farmers, the Bank has a well-defined setup in terms of Farmer's training Centres (FTCs), Rural Self Employment Training

Institutes (RSETIs), and Financial Literacy and Credit Counselling Centres (FLCCs).

3. To channelize the efforts of the Bank in the area of CSR, a separate wing i.e. PNB Prerna has been set up wherein the wives of the senior officers and female employees identify the needy organizations and beneficiaries who deserve to be supported for bringing about a change in the lives of differently-abled people and also people from the lower strata of the society. The CSR activities have been decentralized to circle levels. To encourage innovative ideas, a scheme to recognize the best CSR initiatives of the circles is also put in place.

4. It started emphasizing on green building practices to conserve resources like electricity, water, paper, etc.

5. PNB is putting their best efforts for rainwater harvesting in existing buildings and encourage environment friendly new constructions. Also, promoting wind energy and popularizing solar energy usage in rural areas.

6. Sapling of 3345 plants was executed in the 33 Tree Plantation camps organised during the year.

7. It started emphasizing on green building practices such as energy efficient lights, immediate repair of water leakage, printing on both sides of paper, mater sensors for lights, fans, etc. Purchasing composite fax machines which can perform multiple functions.

8. The organisation had signed a green pledge with Ministry of New and renewable energy under which they had set up the butterfly park at the compound of Guruvayur temple which houses 18 types of medicinal plants.

9. They had formulated guidelines to ensure that all the necessary approvals and permissions, including from the Pollution Control Board has been obtained before the disbursement of term loans and for the project loans, compliance with environment and social safeguards including rehabilitation and resettlement of project-affected people is to be ensured as a pre-disbursement condition.

10. The Bank is also considering sustainable development with particular reference to the Equator Principles on project finance.

Green Products & Services

The Bank is offering green products and services like:

Instabanking-

It is a service that gives convenience to customers to do banking anywhere and anytime through internet banking, mobile banking, IVR banking, etc. This reduces the carbon footprint of the customers as they do not require a physical statement or travel to the bank branches.

Vehicle Finance-

They are offering 50% waiver on processing fee of auto loans on the car models which uses alternate sources of energy like the Civic Hybrid of Honda, Tata Indica CNG, Reva electric cars, Mahindra Logan CNG versions, Maruti's L version of Maruti 800, Omni and Versa, and Hyundai's Santro Eco.

Home Finance

The Bank had reduced the processing fee for the customers who are purchasing homes in LEED certified buildings.

Green Engagements

1. It has also become partners with the green theme CNBC overdrive auto awards.

2. The Bank is celebrating World Environment Day every year on June 5. They perform various activities on that day like green pledge through signature campaigns, plantation and distribution of saplings etc. They are also celebrating earth Hour every year in March in which they switch off lights of their premises, branches and ATM's between 8:30 pm to 9:30pm.

Green Communications

The bank always insists their customers for online bill payment, online funds transfer and subscription to e statements which promote 'paperless' and 'commute free' modes of banking transactions.

Green Partners

1. The organisation is looking forward for partnerships with national and international green organisations and NGO's. They are partners with green governance awards set up by BHNS to appreciate the participant's organisation effort beyond the statutory compliance for protection of the environment.

2. The banking major is also encouraging using CFL bulbs and carpool and public transportation. It also uses online webinars for shorter meetings that involve people who might otherwise have to travel a long distance.

3. Assisted a company in developing a product that provides an eco-friendly air conditioner alternative to conventional air conditioners.

Suggestions that can be adopted by banks to encourage green banking

1. Construct a website and spread the news.
2. Educate through the Bank's Intranet and Public Website.
3. Participate in events.
4. Set up outlets to promote green business.
5. Communicate through the press.
6. Disseminate info through Leaflets.
7. Social responsibility services done by banks.
8. Carbon footprint reduction by energy consciousness.
9. Carbon footprint reduction by mass transportation.
10. Impart education through E-learning programmes.
11. Making it a part of the annual environment report.

Conclusion Green banking is still a major issue and can be important for the development of our country in India. As banks and financial institutions in India have started taking the initiative but not at a high level. To sustain the development of the Indian Economy banks and financial institutions have to work harder. For effective green banking, the RBI and the Indian Government should play a pro active role and formulate green policy guidelines and financial incentives. The survival of the banking industry is inversely proportional to the level of global warming. Therefore, for sustainable banking, Indian banks should adopt green banking as a business model without any further delay. Green banking, if implemented sincerely will act as an effective ex antedeterrent for the polluting industries that give a pass by to the other institutional regulatory mechanisms.

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